

GOBLET

NEWSLETTER

Issue 1 | April 2022

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6467407>

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GOBLET PR

Designed by

Gökçen Şahin

(PRO member)

MESSAGE FROM THE EXECUTIVE BOARD

Dear GOBLET members,

You are receiving the first GOBLET newsletter of 2022, with a brand new look and feel, designed by Gökçen Şahin from the GOBLET PR committee. We hope you will find useful and interesting information and also invite you to send your own news to our GOBLET PR Team (pr@mygoblet.org) to have it featured in upcoming GOBLET newsletters.

Despite the fact that the world was (and still is) facing the pandemic, the GOBLET members have proven to be creative and productive in 2021. The full report about the 2021 activities can be found in the AGM2021 presentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5646886>), but here are a number of events that we want to highlight:

- The [Bioinformatics Education Summit 2021](#) (presentation of outcomes: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5937855>)
- The [ISMB/ECCB2021 WEB](#) Making training materials FAIR experiences, challenges and solutions
- A very successful 10th [GOBLET AGM2021](#)
- GOBLET-ELIXIR [Train-the-Trainer workshop 2021](#)
- [Workshop for Single-Cell RNA-seq Data Analysis Trainers](#)

In addition, the following new Guides that were published:

- [Course design - Considerations for trainers](#) - Via A., Palagi PM, Lindvall JM, Tractenberg RE, Attwood TK, The GOBLET Foundation (2020)
- [Using bioinformatics to hunt SARS-CoV-2, its variants & its origins - a practical guide](#) - Marie-Claude Blatter, Philippe Le Mercier, Teresa K. Attwood, The GOBLET Foundation (2021)

For 2022, we are looking forward to, amongst other things, the Bioinformatics Education Summit 2022, which will be hosted by APBioNET, and also to formalize our collaboration with the ISCB and its Student Council.

At the end of 2021, our Secretary Domenica D'Elia stepped down from the Executive Board. We thank her for all the work she has done for GOBLET. This also means we are looking for new people to strengthen the Executive Board. In addition, as already indicated during the AGM, we need more people to actively get engaged in the GOBLET activities. See further below in this newsletter for more information. We look forward to your active participation.

Wishing you all a very good and productive 2022!

Celia van Gelder,

on behalf of the GOBLET Executive Board

Bioinformatics Education Special Track @ InCoB

By *Wai Keat Yam* (APBioNET, International Medical University Malaysia)

A special Education track was organised as part of the International Conference on Bioinformatics 2021 (InCoB2021) on 7 November 2021. This was the second year of such a special track, an outcome of commitment made by APBioNET in the AGM meeting of GOBLET back in 2019, when it was co-located with InCoB2019.

The first education track was successfully organised during InCoB2021 as a virtual event due to the pandemic. The aim of the education track is to raise awareness of the various bioinformatics education efforts, foster cross-pollination of ideas and inter-community collaborations, and ultimately to expand as wide as possible the beneficiary network of these activities.

For the 2021 track, we invited distinguished speakers, Melissa Burke (Australian BioCommons), Celia W. G. van Gelder (Global Organisation for Bioinformatics Learning, Education & Training, GOBLET), Yo Yehudi (Open Life Science, OLS), Jason Williams (Life Science Trainers, LST) and Wai Keat Yam (Asia-Pacific Bioinformatics Network, APBioNET). The event was attended by over hundreds of participants, both virtually and in person.

The third education track will take place at this year's InCoB2022, to be hosted by KAUST, Saudi Arabia. We are excited for another round of engaging discussions.

Wai Keat Yam

Celia W. G. van Gelder

Yo Yehudi

Jason Williams

Melissa Burke

Workshop for Single-Cell RNA-seq Data Analysis Trainers gathered trainers around the world

Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) offers unprecedented opportunities for life science research, and new experimental technologies and data analysis methods have been developed at a rapid pace. The training needs in this fast moving area are huge. The GOBLET-ELIXIR workshop on 30 November 2021 brought together scRNA-seq trainers from around the world to share experiences, challenges and best practices. The slides are available on the [workshop website](#), and the [presentation videos](#) are available on [GOBLET YouTube channel](#). The workshop was considered very useful, so future collaboration meetings will be planned.

REMINDER AND CALL FOR PARTICIPATION

Time to renew your GOBLET membership

GOBLET Treasurer Eija Korpelainen will soon be sending out the membership invoices for 2022. Please get in touch with her, if there are any changes in your institute's contact details, GOBLET membership level or duration.

Eija Korpelainen
treasurer@mygoblet.org

Call for members to join GOBLET Task forces

We need you to contribute to GOBLET's activities!

Looking at the AGM2021 and more importantly the discussion on [Day 3](#) that was for members only, a large number of possible activities were discussed. We discussed that champions and contributors are needed and it is evident that we can only move further if you are prepared to put in some of your valuable time to bring in your expertise! For this reason, we propose to start GOBLET Task Forces for identified topics we all agree that we want to work on. A Task Force is defined in the GOBLET statutes as a dynamic group whose role is to complete a designated task and/or to make recommendations to GOBLET's operational and/or management bodies.

The GOBLET Task Forces that are currently foreseen are:

- High school activities - new Practical Guides, translation of Guides to other languages, and workshops, among others.
- GOBLET Website editorial team - we need a few people who are willing to form a team (complemented by one member of the EB

and one member of the GOBLET PR team) to discuss, oversee, structure and curate the website content.

- Get acquainted with the EB - with the Secretary stepping down, we are now one member less in the EB. In the upcoming elections at the AGM2022, a new EB will be elected. We offer interested individuals a period from April - October 2022, where they can participate in the EB, get acquainted with GOBLET and its activities, and that way can make an informed decision if they want to stand for election for the EB in October 2022.

In addition, if you are interested and have ideas, we would love to expand the activities on new Professional Guides, new Critical Guides and Fundraising too. And in case you have additional ideas, please do not hesitate to let us know!

If you are interested in committing some time to one of the tasks mentioned above, please let us know via info@mygoblet.org.

UPCOMING EVENTS

Bioinformatics Education Summit 2022

9 - 11 May 2022

The 2022 Bioinformatics Education Summit is happening from 9 to 11 May 2022, over 2 time zones (GMT+8 and GMT-4), virtually! Education experts from all over the world, mainly focusing on bioinformatics, would gather virtually for 3 days to work on pertaining issues in bioinformatics education/training. Do note that this is NOT A CONFERENCE, BUT A WORKING MEETING, where you are expected to actively participate in discussion and writing. The participation is free and open to all people working in the area of

bioinformatics teaching and education or who have a clear interest in contributing to it. Stay tuned for more information and we look forward to your active participation!

This fourth edition of the Bioinformatics Education Summit will be hosted by APBioNET. For more information about what happened in the 2021 edition of the Summit, please see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5937855>

Nordic ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer

10 - 13 May 2022
12.00 - 16.00 CET

This global workshop is organized by the Nordic countries. The participants will learn how to apply learning principles to training, design courses, engage learners, assess and collect feedback. Four days of interesting lessons and fruitful discussions on these topics! Read more on the [workshop website](#).

GOBLET AGM 2022

11 - 14 Oct. 2022

SAVE
THE
DATE

GOBLET AGM 2022 to be held virtually from 11 to 14th October 2022, hosted by Bezmialem Vakif University, Istanbul, Turkey. This year's AGM will be centred around a Colloquium on Bioinformatics Learning, Education and Training (COBLET).

GOBLET MEMBERSHIP

Benefits of Being Part of Us

JOIN AND SUPPORT US!

Our Organisational Members

4273pi
Bioinformatics Education project

Center for Molecular and Biomolecular Informatics (CMBI)

